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“THE ESSENTIALS OF CAPACITORS IN ELECTRONICS”

Modern life is deeply integrated with electronic technologies, which utilize numerous electronic circuits in modern devices. Engineers have designed electronic circuits of the following, but not limited to, power supplies (e.g., linear power supply, switching-mode power supply), signal generators (e.g., analog signal oscillator and digital pulse generator), signal conditioning circuits (e.g., pre-amplifiers and power amplifiers), communication devices (e.g., AM/FM radio, ham radio, mobile phones, and radar), industrial controls (e.g., microcontrollers and power electronics), and computers (e.g., laptops and desktops). Complex electronic circuits comprise resistors, capacitors, diodes, transistors, and inductors, which are interconnected to form important functional electronic devices. Among the circuit components, capacitors are crucial in most electronic devices that require stable signals in every process.

The role of capacitors in linear power-supply circuits is crucial. When alternating current passed through diodes, the AC will be converted to a pulsating DC with that the AC frequency remains and appears in the DC voltage. The ripple DC voltage is cancelled if capacitor is added to the circuit because of its ability to store voltage and override fluctuations by sustaining the stored charge above the fluctuating voltage level. Moreover, switch-mode power supplies (SMPS) use capacitors in several ways, including capacitors combined with resistors or inductors, to help create specific signals to run high-frequency transformers. These transformers are primarily used to convert high-voltage DC into low-voltage AC (commonly called chopper transformers). The transformer can handle varying input-switching drive frequencies while maintaining a constant preset voltage output. Generally, a capacitor is used to set the timing of pulses, owing to its capability to store voltage and release it in a short period of time according to its capacitance value. In contrast, capacitors are also primarily used in signal-generator circuits in the oscillations of new signal frequencies for different purposes. In practical applications, electronic signals and pulses are fundamental to technological advancements. They serve as the heart of electronic systems by delivering precise timing and control necessary for the operation of each process.

Electronics students learn to understand the practical applications of capacitors in school laboratories by experiencing hands-on activities (e.g., circuit experiments and assembling electronic circuits), such as power supplies, where they can observe how a pure DC voltage is created from an AC power source, rectified with diodes, and smoothen using a filter capacitor with a corresponding capacitance value compatible with the circuit. In hands-on experience in the assembly of a signal generator, students observe the characteristics of signals using visualization equipment such as an oscilloscope that displays the signal waveforms and signal frequency. A light-emitting diode (LED) was used to help students see the low-

frequency electronic signals. The LED blinks or pulses in sync with the signal, making the invisible electronic signal visible to the human eye.

Capacitors are essential in electronics because they introduce capacitance, which is primarily used to purify DC power and set the precise timing of pulses in a signal generator, where electronic signal frequencies provide life in every electronic system, whether analog or digital.

